

EXPRESSING EMOTIVE MEANING WITH STYLISTIC DEVICES IN ORAL SPEECH

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to different stylistic devices to express emotive meaning in oral speech. There are different types of stylistic devices which are lexical and phonetical that we use in our usage of language. It is important to know meanings of used different devices. This article deals with understanding various devices according to the meaning in people's daily speech.

Studying and understanding people's speech is more difficult for having different types of meaning of the same word and their role in a sentence varies. It is well known that the study of the sentence and its types and especially the study of the relations between different parts of the sentence has had a long history. Modern grammars have taken under observation the peculiarities of the relations between the members of the sentence, but the study of units of speech larger than the sentence is still being neglected by many linguists. Stylistics takes as the object of its analysis the expressive means and stylistic devices of the language which are based on some significant structural point in an utterance, whether it consists of one sentence or a string of sentences. The peculiarities of the structural design of sentences certainly have some emotional colouring and that's why they are considered stylistic and emotionally coloured. In order to understand the nature of the emotional charge of such syntactical structures, we must be aware of the norm of syntactical usage. By the norm of syntactical usage we mean the rules of the language according to which the word combinations, sentences, super phrasal units, paragraphs and texts constructed.

We study stylistic devices according to their phonetic, semantic, syntactic, and combination of both semantic and syntactic features. Thus we divide them into: 1. Phonetic stylistic devices. 2. Lexical stylistic devices. 3. Syntactic stylistic devices. 4. Lexico-syntactical stylistic devices[4;26]

The stylistic approach to the utterance is not confined to its structure and sense. There is another thing to be taken into account which in a certain type of communication plays an important role. This is the way a word, a phrase or a sentence sounds. The sound of most words taken separately will have little or no aesthetic value. It is in combination with other words that a word may acquire a desired phonetic effect. The way a separate word sounds due to their articulatory and acoustic properties may produce a certain ideas, perceptions,

feelings, images, euphonic effect, but this is a matter of individual perception and feeling and therefore subjective.[7;65] Stylistic phonology investigates those phonetic peculiarities of a language and explains the stylistic functions of them. There are different types of devices.

Phonetic stylistic devices

Onomatopoeia. In the English language, the term onomatopoeia means 'the imitation of a sound'. But in the Greek language, from which the word onomatopoeia comes, means "making or creating names". In Greek for words that imitate sounds, the term echomimetic is used which means 'mimetic or imitation'. Onomatopoeia is a combination of speech sounds which aims at imitating sounds produced in nature (wind, sea, thunder, etc.) by things (machines or tools, etc.) by people (singing, laughter) and animals. It is the choice of sounds capable of suggesting the image of the object by their very sounding, imitating the signified object or action. E.g. Babble, chatter, giggle, whisper, buzz, cackle, croak, crow, hiss, howl, moo, mew, roar, bubble, splash, clink, tinkle, murmur, bump, grumble, sizzle, ding-dong, buzz, bang, cuckoo, tintinnabulation, mew, ping-pong, roar.[8;54]

1. "Then with enormous, shattering rumble, sludge-puff, sludge-puff, the train came into the station." (A. Saxton)
2. "... where white horses and black horses and brown horses and white and black horses and brown and white horses trotted tap-tap-tap tap-tap-tappety-tap over cobble stones ..." (Shon O'Casey)
3. "The pretty birds do sing-cuckoo, jug-jug, pee-we, to-witta-woo!" (Shon O'Casey)

There are two varieties of onomatopoeia: direct and indirect. Direct onomatopoeia is contained in words that imitate natural sounds, as dingdong, burr, bang, cuckoo. Indirect onomatopoeia is a combination of words the aim of which is to make the sound of the utterance an echo of its sense. It is sometimes called echo writing: "And the silken, sad, uncertain rustling of each purple curtain" (Edgar Poe), where the repetition of the sound [s] actually produces the sound of the rustling of the curtain. The same can be said of the sounds [u] and [o] produced by the soldiers marching over Africa: "We are foot-slog-slog-slog-slogging Foot-foot-foot-foot-slogging over Africa. Boots- boots- boots- boots - moving up and down again. (Rudyard Kipling)

Alliteration is derived from Latin word Latira and means 'letters of alphabet'. It is a stylistic device in which a number of words, having the same first consonant sound, occur close together in a series of multiple words, or the repetition of the same letter sounds in stressed syllables of a phrase. "The fair breeze blew, the white foam flew, The furrow followed free; We were the first that ever burst Into that silent sea." (Samuel Taylor Coleridge) In the above lines we see alliteration ("b", "f" and "s") in the phrases breeze blew, foam flew, furrow followed, and silent sea.

In our daily conversation, we notice alliteration in the names of different companies. It makes the name of a company catchy and easy to memorize. Here are several common alliteration examples. PayPal, Best Buy, Coca-Cola, Bed and Breakfast.

Assonance comes from Latin word assonantem which means 'to respond to, to be in harmony'. It is a repetition of similar vowels, usually in stressed syllables of the word. Assonance takes place when two or more words close to one another repeat the same vowel sound but start with different consonant sounds.

She seems to beam rays of sunshine with her eyes of green.

In this example, the speaker uses assonance to describe a pretty woman. Assonance occurs in the repeating vowel sounds of seems, beam, and green.

Lexical stylistic devices

Metaphor comes from the Greek word metaphore which means 'transference bearing'. Metaphor is based on a relation between the dictionary and contextual logical meanings based on the affinity or similarity of certain properties or features of the two corresponding concepts. Here transference of names is based on the associated likeness between two objects, as in the 'pancake', 'ball', 'volcano' for 'the sun'; 'silver dust', 'sequins' for 'stars'; 'vault', 'blanket', 'veil' for 'the sky'. [1;89] Metaphor can be embodied in all the meaningful parts of speech, in nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs.

Here some examples of metaphor that we can use in our speech.

1. Knowledge is light. It eliminates the darkness of ignorance and lack of understanding.
2. Knowledge is Love
3. Knowledge is power
4. Time is a parade. It marches forward, no matter how big the crowd, no matter how many or few cheers there are, and no matter what the weather. Using time wisely means ignoring all of these distractions.
5. Time is an enemy for those who waste it.
6. Time is a trap, I'm caught in it.

Metonymy is based on a different types of relations between the dictionary and contextual meanings, a relation is based on association connecting the two concepts and these meanings represent proximity. The clear example of metonymy is as follows:

The pen is mightier than the sword.

However, there are a lot of words in English language to express another meaning to attract the attention and create emotive meaning.

Crown	in place of a royal person	We will swear loyalty to the crown.
The White House or The Oval Office	used in place of the President or White House staff	The White House will be making an announcement around noon.
Suits	in place of businesspeople	If we don't get these reports in today, the suits will be after us.
Heart	to refer to love or emotion	My dear, you have all of my heart.
Dish	for an entire plate of food	That fancy fish dish you made was the best of the evening.
Washington	to refer to the U.S. government	After the protests, maybe Washington will listen to the voters.
the big house	to refer to prison	My brother was just released from the big house.
Silicon Valley	to refer to the tech industry	Silicon Valley is constantly pushing the boundaries in innovation.
Hollywood	to refer to the film industry	It seems like people will do

		whatever Hollywood says is cool.
Ears	for giving attention, listening	Tell me about your first date. I'm all ears!
silver fox	for an attractive older man	Your older neighbor is quite the silver fox.
Hand	for help	Can you give me a hand carrying this box up the stairs?
Tongue	used in place of language	I couldn't understand them, they spoke in their mother tongue.
Brass	used in place of high-ranking officials	Look lively, the top brass are coming for an audit today.
new blood	used in place of new people, fresh ideas	The team needs some new blood if it's going to win next season.

Irony comes from the Greek word meaning 'slight mockery'. Irony is based on the simultaneous realization of two logical meanings - dictionary and contextual, but the two meanings are in opposition to each other. The literal meaning is the opposite of the intended meaning, that is why irony is based on the opposition of what is said to what is meant.

"It must be delightful to find oneself in a foreign country without a penny in one's pocket."

"What a fine musician you turned out to be!,"

"It's like you're a whole different person now...,"

Functions of irony. Irony is often used in literature to produce a comic effect. This may also be combined with satire [5;93] An author may facetiously state something as a wellknown fact and then demonstrate through the narrative that the fact is untrue.

- A post on Instagram statehouse useless its algorithm is.

You will come across such sentences while scrolling through social media every day but what's ironic is that despite Instagram 's algorithm being useless, you still see that post about its algorithm being useless. Did you get it?

- A math teacher cannot solve math problems.

Well, the sentence is ironic because you will expect a math teacher to be an expert in that subject and despite being the teacher of mathematics, he failed to solve some math problems. I guess he just needs to work it out.

- The pilot has a height phobia.

This is it given right? A pilot whose job is to be in the Heights both literally and figuratively is scared of heights. So, how will the pilot do his job?

Paradox comes from the Greek word 'paradoxon' which means 'unexpected'. It is a statement that appears to be self-contradictory or silly but may include a latent truth. It is also used to illustrate an opinion or statement contrary to accepted traditional ideas. A paradox is often used to make a reader think over an idea in innovative way. In literature, paradox is not just a clever or comical statement or use of words. Paradox has serious implication because it makes statements that often summarize the major themes of the work they are used in.

1. "All animals are equal, but some are more equal than others".(George Orwell)
2. "I must be cruel to be kind."

3. "I think that life is far too important a thing ever to talk seriously about it." (Oscar Wilde)

Another example that we always use in our speech: Optimist is a pessimist with experience.

Simile comes from Latin word *similis* which means 'alike'. It is an imaginative comparison of two objects belonging to two different classes. Unlike a metaphor, a simile draws resemblance with the help of the words 'like, as, as though, as like, such as, as...as'. Therefore, it is a direct comparison.

A simile usually consists of these components:

1. Tenor – the subject under discussion (the one which is compared).
2. Vehicle – what the subject is compared to (the one with which it is compared).
3. Ground – what the poet believes that the tenor and the vehicle have in common.

She is happy as a lark out of cage.

Tenor Ground Vehicle

1. "He remembered the dog whose eyes were as big as saucers" (Michael Ondaatje)
2. "And I could write like the wind – stories and poems, diaries, letters." (Jay Parini)
3. "But what can one expect from a woman like her, who wastes her days snuffling around behind Leo Nikolayevich's back like a dog, trying to unearth some new bone of discord." (Jay Parini)
4. "Exile is a great Russian institution. The Russian soul has been tempered, like blue steel, in Siberia." (Jay Parini)

Similes enrich English phraseology: 'Like a squirrel in a cage', 'to sleep like a dog', 'busy as a bee', 'blind as a bat', 'bald as an egg'. These phraseological units are trite similes.

- As cold as ice
- Swim like a fish
- As light as a feather
- Fight like cats and dogs
- As cool as a cucumber
- Like two peas in a pod
- As black as coal
- Cheap as chips
- As busy as a bee
- I know this like the back of my hand

Oxymoron is a literary figure of speech in which opposite or contradictory words, terms, phrases or ideas are combined to create a rhetorical effect by paradoxical means. For example, despairing hope, tender cruelty, glad mourning and sad joy

Accordingly, Oxymorons are also a part of our daily speech, like absent presence, alone together, awful good. In this respect, Abram argues that an oxymoron is a figure of speech in which seemingly contradictory terms appear side by side like other kinds of figurative language.

What distinguishes oxymoron from other paradoxes and contradictions is that they are used intentionally, for rhetorical effect, and the contradiction is only apparent, as the combination of terms provides a novel expression of some concept. Oxymoron can also be wooden ironies in that they are in violation of the principle of contradiction which asserts that

nothing can be thought if it contains contradictory characteristics, predicates, attributes, or qualities.

Oxymoron is derived from Greek oxumōron, oxus sharp + mōros stupid. In the original form the compound word consists of contradicting ideas. That is why, the essence of the term consists of opposition. Oxymoron is a combination of two words in which the meaning is opposite in sense. Speaking silence, cold fire, living death, beautiful sorrow, busy idleness, stormy silence, horribly beautiful. "And faith unfaithful kept him falsely true"(Alfred Tennyson).

In oxymoron the emotive meaning suppresses the logical meaning. But it should be noted that the logical meaning being suppressed is not lost completely. If the logical meaning is lost there, there is no SD or we call it the trite oxymoron. For example: in word combinations: awfully nice, awfully glad, terribly sorry, the words awfully and terribly have lost their primary logical meaning and now used with emotive meaning only as intensifiers. Genuine oxymoron is a SD and it is an individual creation.

Sometimes the tendency to use Oxymoron is the mark of certain literary trends and tastes. There are poets in search of new shades of meaning in existing words, who make a point of joining together words of contradictory meaning. "Two ordinary words may become almost new", writes V.V.Vinogradov, "if they are joined for the first time or used in an unexpected context". Thus "peopled desert"; "populous solitude" (Byron) are oxymoronic. Not every combination of words should be regarded as oxymoron, because new meanings developed in new combinations do not necessarily give rise to opposition. Rather often oxymoron's are met within a simile. E.g.: He was gentle as hell. An oxymoron always exposes the author's subjective attitude. In such cases two opposite ideas very naturally repulse each other, so that a once created oxymoron is practically never repeated in different contexts and so does not become trite, always remaining a free combination.

The poorest millionaires "There were some bookcases of superbly unreadable book, a gun, a butterfly net, an alpenstock in the corner." (Evelyn Waugh) Sprinting towards the elevator he felt amazed at his own cowardly courage[8;41]

For Galperin [4;66], oxymoron is a rhetorical device that summarizes the idea of semantic paradox. Oxymoron is the essence of semantic contradiction whose variants are the paradox and the antithesis. One can say that oxymoron is a semantic approximation of opposites[9;123]Grammatical features of oxymaron

Oxymoron has the following structure models:

1. Adjective + noun – an honest lie, Ill health, Deafening silence, Classic novel, Extinct life, Artificial Intelligence, Loose tights, Free love, Boneless Ribs, Casual Dress, Close Distance, Common Sense, Holy war Homeless shelter
2. Adverb + adjective – pleasantly ugly, horribly beautiful, Approximately Equal, Awfully Nice, Awfully Good, Clearly confused, Classically modern, Fairly dark, Hopelessly Optimistic, Legally Drunk, Partially Complete, Virtually Identical, Terribly Pleased.
3. Noun of noun – paradise of our despair, vitality of a person,
4. Verb + adverb – she cried silently.

The stylistic approach to the utterance is not confined to its structure and sense. There is another thing to be taken into account which in a certain type of communication plays an

important role.[10;79] This is the way a word, a phrase or a sentence sounds. The sound of most words taken separately will have little or no aesthetic value. It is in combination with other words that a word may acquire a desired phonetic effect. Stylistic semasiology deals with those semantic changes and relations, which create an additional, connotative meaning. Stylistic semasiology analyses and classifies stylistic devices from the point of view of the mechanism of different semantic changes and their stylistic functions.

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